

A MIXING OF PROUHET-THUE-MORSE SEQUENCES AND RADEMACHER FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

We present a novel generalization of the Prouhet-Thue-Morse sequence to binary ± 1 -weight sequences. Derived from Rademacher functions, these weight sequences are shown to satisfy interesting orthogonality and recurrence relations. In addition, we establish a result useful in radar by describing these weight sequences as sidelobes of Doppler tolerant waveforms.

1. Introduction

Let $u(n)$ denote the binary sum-of-digits residue function, i.e., the sum of the digits in the binary expansion of n modulo 2. For example, $u(7) = u(111_2) = 3 \bmod 2 = 1$. The sequence $u(n)$ is known as the Prouhet-Thue-Morse (PTM) integer sequence. It can easily be shown to satisfy the recurrence

$$\begin{aligned} u(0) &= 0 \\ u(2n) &= u(n) \\ u(2n+1) &= 1 - u(n). \end{aligned}$$

The first few terms of $u(n)$ are 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1. Observe that the PTM sequence can also be generated by starting with the value 0 and recursively appending a negated copy of itself (bitwise):

$$0 \rightarrow 01 \rightarrow 0110 \rightarrow 01101001 \rightarrow \dots$$

Another approach to defining the PTM sequence is to iterate the morphism μ defined on the alphabet $\{0, 1\}$ using the substitution rules $\mu(0) = 01$ and $\mu(1) = 10$

(see [1]). Beginning with $x_0 = 0$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= \mu(x_0) = 01 \\ x_2 &= \mu^2(x_0) = \mu(x_1) = 0110 \\ x_3 &= \mu^3(x_0) = \mu(x_2) = 01101001 \\ &\dots \end{aligned}$$

This *ubiquitous* sequence, coined as such by Allouche and Shallit [1], first arose in the works of three mathematicians: Prouhet [22] involving equal sums of like powers in 1851, Thue [28] on combinatorics of words in 1906, and Morse [18] in differential geometry in 1921. It has found interesting applications in many areas of mathematics, physics, and engineering: combinatorial game theory (see, e.g., [20] on fair division and [9] on infinite play in chess, and [1], p. 3), fractals (see, e.g., [3, 15]), quasicrystals (see, e.g., [17, 25]) and more recently Doppler tolerant waveforms in radar (see, e.g., [6, 19, 21]).

Suppose we now replace the 0's and 1's in the PTM sequence with 1's and -1 's, respectively. This yields the ± 1 -sequence $w(n)$, a sequence that clearly satisfies the recurrence

$$\begin{aligned} w(0) &= 1 \\ w(2n) &= w(n) \\ w(2n + 1) &= -w(n). \end{aligned}$$

Here, $w(n)$ and $u(n)$ are related by

$$w(n) = 1 - 2u(n). \tag{1}$$

It is easy to verify that (1) is equivalent to

$$w(n) = (-1)^{u(n)}. \tag{2}$$

Of course, $u(n)$ can be generalized to any modulus $p \geq 2$. Towards this end, we define $u_p(n)$ to be the sum of the digits in the base- p expansion of n modulo p . We shall call $u_p(n)$ the mod- p PTM integer sequence. Then $u_p(n)$ satisfies the recurrence

$$\begin{aligned} u_p(0) &= 0 \\ u_p(pn + r) &= (u(n) + r)_p, \end{aligned}$$

where $(m)_p \equiv m \pmod p$ and $(m)_p \in [0, p - 1]$. More interestingly, it is well known that $u_p(n)$ provides a solution to the famous Prouhet-Tarry-Escott (PTS) problem ([14, 22, 30]): given a positive integer M , find p mutually disjoint sets of non-negative integers S_0, S_1, \dots, S_{p-1} so that

$$\sum_{n \in S_0} n^m = \sum_{n \in S_1} n^m = \dots = \sum_{n \in S_{p-1}} n^m$$

for $m = 1, \dots, M$. The solution, first given by Prouhet [22] and later proven by Lehmer [14] (see also Wright [30]), is to partition the integers $\{0, 1, \dots, p^{M+1} - 1\}$ so that $n \in S_{u_p(n)}$. For example, if $M = 3$ and $p = 2$, then the two sets $S_0 = \{0, 3, 5, 6, 9, 10, 12, 15\}$ and $S_1 = \{1, 2, 4, 7, 8, 11, 13, 14\}$ given by Prouhet's result solve the PTS problem, namely,

$$\begin{aligned} 60 &= 0 + 3 + 5 + 6 + 9 + 10 + 12 + 15 \\ &= 1 + 2 + 4 + 7 + 8 + 11 + 13 + 14 \\ 620 &= 0^2 + 3^2 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 10^2 + 12^2 + 15^2 \\ &= 1^2 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 8^2 + 11^2 + 13^2 + 14^2 \\ 7200 &= 0^3 + 3^3 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 10^3 + 12^3 + 15^3 \\ &= 1^3 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 7^3 + 8^3 + 11^3 + 13^3 + 14^3. \end{aligned}$$

In this paper, we address the following question: what is the natural generalization of $w(n)$ to modulus $p \geq 2$? Which formula should we look to extend, (1) or (2)? Is there any intuition behind our generalization? One answer is to define $w_p(n)$ by merely replacing $u(n)$ with $u_p(n)$ in say (2). However, to discover a more satisfying answer, we consider a modified form of (2):

$$w(n) = (-1)^{d_{1-u(n)}}. \tag{3}$$

Here, $d_{1-u(n)}$ takes on one of two possible values, $d_0 = 1$ or $d_1 = 0$, which we view as the first two digits in the binary expansion (base 2) of the number 1, i.e., $1 = d_1 2^1 + d_0 2^0$. Thus, formula (3) involves the digit opposite in position to $u(n)$.

To explain how this formula naturally generalizes to any positive modulus $p \geq 2$, we begin our story with two arbitrary elements a_0 and a_1 . Define $A = (a_n) = (a_0, a_1, \dots)$ to be what we call a mod-2 PTM sequence generated from a_0 and a_1 , where the elements of A satisfy the aperiodic condition

$$a_n = a_{u(n)}.$$

Thus, $A = (a_0, a_1, a_1, a_0, a_1, a_0, a_0, a_1, \dots)$. Since formula (3) holds, it follows that a_n can be decomposed as

$$a_n = \frac{1}{2}(a_0 + a_1) + \frac{1}{2}w(n)(a_0 - a_1). \tag{4}$$

In some sense, $w(n)$ plays the same role as $u(n)$ in defining the sequence A , but through the decomposition (4). We argue that formula (4) leads to a natural generalization of $w(n)$. For example, suppose $p = 3$ and consider the mod-3 PTM sequence $A = (a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots)$ generated by three elements a_0, a_1, a_2 so that $a_n = a_{u_3(n)}$. The

following decomposition generalizes (4):

$$a_n = \frac{1}{4}w_0(n)(a_0 + a_1 + a_2) + \frac{1}{4}w_1(n)(a_0 + a_1 - a_2) + \frac{1}{4}w_2(n)(a_0 - a_1 + a_2) + \frac{1}{4}w_3(n)(a_0 - a_1 - a_2).$$

Here, $w_0(n), w_1(n), w_2(n), w_3(n)$ are ± 1 -sequences that we shall call the weights of a_n . Since $a_n = a_{u_3(n)}$, these weights are fully specified once their values are known for $n = 0, 1, 2$. It is straightforward to verify in this case that $W(n) = (w_0(n), \dots, w_3(n))$ takes on the values

$$\begin{aligned} W(0) &= (1, 1, 1, 1) \\ W(1) &= (1, 1, -1, -1) \\ W(2) &= (1, -1, 1, -1). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the weights $w_i(n)$ are a natural generalization of $w(n)$.

More generally, if $p \geq 2$ is a positive integer and $A = (a_n)$ is a mod- p PTM sequence generated from a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{p-1} , i.e., $a_n = a_{u_p(n)}$, then the following decomposition holds:

$$a_n = \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i^{(p)}(n) B_i. \tag{5}$$

Here, the weights $w_i^{(p)}$ are given by

$$w_i(n) := w_i^{(p)}(n) = (-1)^{d_{p-1-u_p(n)}^{(i)}}, \tag{6}$$

where $0 \leq i \leq 2^{p-1} - 1$ and $i = d_{p-2}^{(i)}2^{p-2} + \dots + d_1^{(i)}2^1 + d_0^{(i)}2^0$ denotes its binary expansion. Moreover, B_i is calculated by the formula

$$B_i = \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} w_i(n) a_n. \tag{7}$$

Observe that we can extend the range for i to $2^p - 1$ (and will do so), effectively doubling the number of weights w_i . In that case we find that

$$w_i(n) = -w_{2^p-1-i}(n).$$

With this extension, we demonstrate in Theorem 16 that each $w_i(n)$ satisfies the recurrence

$$w_i(pn + r) = w_{x_r(i)}(n)w_i(n),$$

where $x_r(i)$ denotes a quantity that we define in Section 4 as the *xor-shift* of i by r , where $0 \leq x_r(i) \leq 2^p - 1$. For example, if $p = 2$, we find that

$$\begin{aligned} w_1(2n) &= w_0(n)w_1(n) \\ w_1(2n + 1) &= w_3(n)w_1(n). \end{aligned}$$

Since $w_0(n) = 1$ and $w_3(n) = -1$ for all n , this yields the same recurrence satisfied by $w(n) = w_1(n)$ as described in the beginning of this section.

Next, we note that the set of values $R(n) = (w_0(n), \dots, w_{2^p-1}(n))$ represent those given by the Rademacher functions $\phi_n(x)$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, defined by (see [11, 23])

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_0(x) &= 1 \quad (0 \leq x < 1/2), & \phi_0(x+1) &= \phi_0(x); \\ \phi_0(x) &= -1 \quad (1/2 \leq x < 1), & \phi_n(x) &= \phi_0(2^n x). \end{aligned}$$

In particular,

$$w_i(n) = \phi_n(i/2^p)$$

so that the right-hand side of (5) can be thought of as a discrete *Rademacher* transform of $(B_0, B_1, \dots, B_{2^p-1})$. Moreover, formula (7) can be viewed as the inverse transform, which follows from the fact that the Rademacher functions form an orthogonal set. Thus, weight sequences can be viewed as a mixing of Prouhet-Thue-Morse sequences and Rademacher functions.

It is known that the Rademacher functions generate the Walsh functions, which have important applications in communications and coding theory (see [4, 27]). Walsh functions are those of the form (see, e.g., [11, 29])

$$\psi_m(x) = \phi_{n_k}(x)\phi_{n_{k-1}}(x) \cdots \phi_{n_1}(x),$$

where $m = 2^{n_k} + 2^{n_{k-1}} + \dots + 2^{n_1}$ with $n_i < n_{i+1}$ for all $i = 1, \dots, k - 1$. This allows us to generalize our weights $w_i(n)$ to sequences

$$\tilde{w}_i(m) = w_i(n_k) \cdots w_i(n_1),$$

which we view as a discrete version of the Walsh functions in the variable i . In that case, we prove in Section 3 that if $0 \leq m \leq 2^p - 1$ for some fixed non-negative integer p , then

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2^p-1} \tilde{w}_i(m) B_i = \begin{cases} a_n, & \text{if } m = 2^n, 0 \leq n \leq p - 1; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We also prove in the same section a result that was used in [19] to characterize these weight sequences as sidelobes of Doppler tolerant radar waveforms (motivated by [6] and [21]).

Lastly, we note that the literature contains many generalizations of the PTM sequence (see, e.g., [2, 13, 26] and more recently, [5, 8, 16]). However, a search of the literature did not reveal any work similar to this article.

2. The Prouhet-Thue-Morse Sequence

Let $S(L)$ denote the set consisting of the first L non-negative integers $0, 1, \dots, L-1$.

Definition 1. Let $n = n_1 n_2 \dots n_k$ be the base- p representation of a non-negative integer n . We define the *mod- p sum-of-digits function* $u_p(n) \in \mathbb{Z}_p$ to be the sum of the digits n_i modulo p , i.e.,

$$u_p(n) \equiv \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \pmod{p}.$$

Observe that $u_p(n) = n$ if $0 \leq n < p$.

Definition 2. We define a sequence $A = (a_0, a_1, \dots)$ to be a *mod- p Prouhet-Thue-Morse (PTM) sequence* if it satisfies the aperiodic condition

$$a_n = a_{u_p(n)}.$$

Definition 3. Let p and M be positive integers and set $L = p^{M+1}$. We define $\{S_0, S_1, \dots, S_{p-1}\}$ to be a *Prouhet-Thue-Morse (PTM) p -block partition* of $S(L) = \{0, 1, \dots, L-1\}$ as follows: if $u_p(n) = i$, then

$$n \in S_i.$$

The next theorem solves the famous Prouhet-Tarry-Escott problem.

Theorem 4 ([22], [14], [30]). *Let p and M be positive integers and set $L = p^{M+1}$. Suppose $\{S_0, S_1, \dots, S_{p-1}\}$ is a PTM p -block partition of $S(L) = \{0, 1, \dots, L-1\}$. Then*

$$P_m := \sum_{n \in S_0} n^m = \sum_{n \in S_1} n^m = \dots = \sum_{n \in S_{p-1}} n^m$$

for $m = 1, \dots, M$. We shall refer to P_m as the m -th Prouhet sum corresponding to p and M .

Corollary 1. *Let $A = (a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{L-1})$ be a mod- p PTM sequence of length $L = p^{M+1}$, where M is a non-negative integer. Then*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m a_n = P_m(a_0 + a_1 + \dots + a_{p-1}) \tag{8}$$

for $m = 0, \dots, M$.

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m a_n &= \sum_{n \in S_0} n^m a_{u_p(n)} + \sum_{n \in S_1} n^m a_{u_p(n)} + \cdots + \sum_{n \in S_{p-1}} n^m a_{u_p(n)} \\ &= a_0 \sum_{n \in S_0} n^m + a_1 \sum_{n \in S_1} n^m + \cdots + a_{p-1} \sum_{n \in S_{p-1}} n^m \\ &= P_m(a_0 + a_1 + \cdots + a_{p-1}). \end{aligned}$$

□

3. Weight Sequences

In this section we develop a generalization of the PTM ± 1 -sequence $w(n)$ and derive orthogonality and recurrence relations for these generalized sequences that we refer to as *weight* sequences.

Definition 5. Let $i = d_{p-1}^{(i)}2^{p-1} + d_{p-2}^{(i)}2^{p-2} + \cdots + d_1^{(i)}2^1 + d_0^{(i)}2^0$ be the binary expansion of i , where i is a non-negative integer with $0 \leq i \leq 2^p - 1$. Define $w_0^{(p)}(n), w_1^{(p)}(n), \dots, w_{2^p-1}^{(p)}(n)$ be binary ± 1 -sequences defined by

$$w_i^{(p)}(n) := w_i(n) = (-1)^{d_{p-1}^{(i)} - u_p(n)}.$$

Example 6. Let $p = 3$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} w_0(n) &= (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, \dots) \\ w_1(n) &= (\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, 1, -1, 1, -1, 1, \dots) \\ w_2(n) &= (\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, -1, 1, 1, 1, -1, \dots) \\ w_3(n) &= (\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, -1, -1, 1, -1, 1, -1, \dots) \\ w_4(n) &= (-\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, 1, 1, -1, 1, -1, 1, \dots) \\ w_5(n) &= (-\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, 1, -1, -1, -1, -1, 1, \dots) \\ w_6(n) &= (-\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}, -1, 1, -1, 1, -1, -1, \dots) \\ w_7(n) &= (-\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, -\mathbf{1}, -1, -1, -1, -1, -1, -1, \dots). \end{aligned}$$

Observe that the first three values of each weight $w_i(n)$ (displayed in bold) represent the binary value of i if we replace 1 and -1 with 0 and 1, respectively. Moreover, we have the following symmetry:

Lemma 1. For $i = 0, 1, \dots, 2^p - 1$, we have

$$w_i(n) = -w_{2^p-1-i}(n).$$

Proof. If $i = d_{p-1}^{(i)}2^{p-1} + d_{p-2}^{(i)}2^{p-2} + \dots + d_0^{(i)}2^0$, then $j = 2^p - 1 - i$ has expansion

$$j = \bar{d}_{p-1}^{(j)}2^{p-1} + \bar{d}_{p-2}^{(j)}2^{p-2} + \dots + \bar{d}_0^{(j)}2^0,$$

where $\bar{d}_k^{(j)} = 1 - d_k^{(i)}$. It follows that

$$w_i(n) = (-1)^{d_{p-1-u_p(n)}^{(i)}} = (-1)^{1-d_{p-1-u_p(n)}^{(j)}} = -w_{2^p-1-i}(n).$$

□

Theorem 7. *Let $p \geq 2$ be a positive integer. Then the vectors $W_p(0), W_p(1), \dots, W_p(p-1)$ defined by*

$$W_p(n) = (w_0^{(p)}(n), w_1^{(p)}(n), \dots, w_{2^{p-1}-1}^{(p)}(n))$$

form an orthogonal set, i.e., for $0 \leq n, m \leq p-1$, we have

$$W_p(n) \cdot W_p(m) = \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n)w_i(m) = 2^{p-1}\delta_{n-m} = \begin{cases} 2^{p-1}, & n = m; \\ 0, & n \neq m. \end{cases}$$

Here, δ_n is the Kronecker delta function.

Proof. It is straightforward to check that the lemma is true for $p = 2$. Thus, we assume $p \geq 3$ and define $k(n) = p - 1 - n$ so that

$$W_p(n) \cdot W_p(m) = \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_{k(n)}^{(i)}+d_{k(m)}^{(i)}}.$$

Assume $n \neq m$ and without loss of generality, take $n < m$ so that $k(n) > k(m)$. Assume $0 \leq i \leq 2^{p-1} - 1$ and expand i in binary so that

$$i = d_{p-1}^{(i)}2^{p-1} + \dots + d_{k(n)}^{(i)}2^{k(n)} + \dots + d_{k(m)}^{(i)}2^{k(m)} + \dots + d_0^{(i)}2^0,$$

where $d_{p-1}^{(i)} = 0$. Suppose in specifying i we fix the choice of values for all binary digits except for $d_{k(n)}^{(i)}$ and $d_{k(m)}^{(i)}$. Then the set $S = \{(0, 0), (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1)\}$ consists of the four possibilities for choosing these two remaining digits, which we express as the ordered pair $d = (d_{k(n)}^{(i)}, d_{k(m)}^{(i)})$. But then the contribution from this set of four such values for i sums to zero in the dot product $W_p(n) \cdot W_p(m)$, namely

$$\sum_{d \in S} (-1)^{d_{k(n)}^{(i)}+d_{k(m)}^{(i)}} = 0.$$

Since this holds for all cases in specifying i , it follows that $W_p(n) \cdot W_p(m) = 0$ as desired. On the other hand, if $n = m$, then $k(n) = k(m)$ and so $d_{k(n)}^{(i)} = d_{k(m)}^{(i)}$ for all i . It follows that

$$W_p(n) \cdot W_p(m) = \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{2d_{k(n)}^{(i)}} = \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} 1 = 2^{p-1}.$$

□

In fact, we have the more general result, which states a discrete version of the fact that the Walsh functions form an orthogonal set.

Theorem 8. *Let m be an integer and expand $m = 2^{n_k} + 2^{n_{k-1}} + \dots + 2^{n_1}$ in binary with $n_i < n_{i+1}$ and $0 \leq m \leq 2^p - 1$. Define*

$$\tilde{w}_i(m) = w_i(n_k) \cdots w_i(n_1)$$

for $i = 0, 1, \dots, 2^p - 1$. Then

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m) = 0 \tag{9}$$

for all $m = 0, 1, \dots, 2^p - 1$.

Proof. Let $m = 2^{n_k} + 2^{n_{k-1}} + \dots + 2^{n_1}$. We argue by induction on k , i.e., the number of distinct powers of 2 in the binary expansion of m . Suppose $k = 1$ and define $q = p - 1 - u_p(n_1)$. Then given any value of i where the binary digit $d_q^{(i)} = 0$, there exists a corresponding value j whose binary digit $d_q^{(j)} = 1$. It follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m) &= \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ d_q^{(i)}=0}}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_q^{(i)}} + \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ d_q^{(i)}=1}}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_q^{(i)}} \\ &= 2^{p-2} - 2^{p-2} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Next, assume that (9) holds for all m consisting of $k - 1$ distinct powers of 2. Define $q_k = p - 1 - u_p(n_k)$. Then for m consisting of k distinct powers of 2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m) &= \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_{q_k}^{(i)} + d_{q_{k-1}}^{(i)} + \dots + d_{q_1}^{(i)}} \\ &= (-1)^0 \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ d_{q_k}^{(i)}=0}}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_{q_{k-1}}^{(i)} + \dots + d_{q_1}^{(i)}} + (-1)^1 \sum_{\substack{i=0 \\ d_{q_k}^{(i)}=1}}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_{q_{k-1}}^{(i)} + \dots + d_{q_1}^{(i)}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_{q_{k-1}}^{(i)} + \dots + d_{q_1}^{(i)}} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} (-1)^{d_{q_{k-1}}^{(i)} + \dots + d_{q_1}^{(i)}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot 0 - \frac{1}{2} \cdot 0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

□

In [24], Richman observed that the classical PTM sequence $u(i)$ (although he did not recognize it by name in his paper) can be constructed from the product of all

Radamacher functions up to order $p - 1$, where $0 \leq i \leq 2^p - 1$. This result easily follows from our formulation of weight sequences since

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{w}_i^{(p)}(2^p - 1) &= w_i^{(p)}(0)w_i^{(p)}(1) \cdots w_i^{(p)}(p - 1) \\ &= (-1)^{d_{p-1}^{(i)} + d_{p-2}^{(i)} + \cdots + d_0^{(i)}} \\ &= (-1)^{u(i)} \\ &= w(i). \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, in the same paper Richman defines a set of difference (DIF) functions given by

$$\text{DIF}(n, j) = (-1)^{s(j)},$$

where $0 \leq j < 2^n$, $j = \sum_{i=0}^n j_i 2^i$ is the binary expansion of j and $s(j) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} j_i$ is the sum-of-digits function. Since $(-1)^{s(j)} = (-1)^{u(j)}$, this shows that $\text{DIF}(n, j) = w(j)$.

Next, we relate weight sequences with PTM sequences. Since $w_i(n) = -w_{p-1-i}(n)$ from Lemma 1, the following lemma is immediate.

Lemma 2. *Let $A = (a_0, a_1, \dots)$ be a mod- p PTM sequence. Define*

$$B_i = \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} w_i(n)a_n$$

for $i = 0, 1, \dots, 2^p - 1$. Then

$$B_i(n) = -B_{2^p-1-i}(n).$$

Theorem 9. *The following equation holds for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$:*

$$a_n = \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n)B_i. \tag{10}$$

Proof. Since $a_n = a_{u_p(n)}$ for a PTM sequence and $w_i(n) = w_i(u_p(n))$, it suffices to prove (10) for $n = 0, 1, \dots, p - 1$. It follows from Theorem 7 that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n)B_i &= \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n) \left(\sum_{m=0}^{p-1} w_i(m)a_m \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} \sum_{m=0}^{p-1} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n)w_i(m) \right) a_m \\ &= \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} \sum_{m=0}^{p-1} 2^{p-1} \delta_{n-m} a_m \\ &= a_n. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark. Because of the lemma above, we will refer to $w_0(n), w_1(n), \dots, w_{2^{p-1}-1}(n)$ as the PTM weights of a_n with respect to the basis of sums $(B_0, B_1, \dots, B_{2^{p-1}-1})$.

Example 10.

1. $p = 2$:

$$\begin{aligned} B_0 &= a_0 + a_1 \\ B_1 &= a_0 - a_1. \end{aligned}$$

2. $p = 3$:

$$\begin{aligned} B_0 &= a_0 + a_1 + a_2, & B_2 &= a_0 - a_1 + a_2, \\ B_1 &= a_0 + a_1 - a_2, & B_3 &= a_0 - a_1 - a_2. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 11. For $0 \leq m \leq 2^p - 1$, we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2^p-1} \tilde{w}_i(m)B_i = \begin{cases} a_n, & \text{if } m = 2^n, 0 \leq n \leq p-1; \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \tag{11}$$

Proof. If $m = 2^n$, then $\tilde{w}_i(n) = w_i(n)$ and thus formula (11) reduces to (10). Therefore, assume $m = 2^{n_k} + \dots + 2^{n_1}$ where $k > 1$. Define $S_m = \{0, 1, \dots, p-1\} - \{n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k\}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m)B_i &= \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n_k) \cdots w_i(n_1) \left(\sum_{j=0}^{p-1} w_i(j)a_j \right) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n_k) \cdots w_i(n_1)w_i(j) \right) a_j. \end{aligned}$$

Next, isolate the terms in the outer summation above corresponding to S_m :

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m)B_i &= a_{n_1} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n_k) \cdots w_i(n_2)w_i(n_1)^2 + \cdots \\ &\quad + a_{n_k} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n_k)^2 w_i(n_{k-1}) \cdots w_i(n_1) \\ &\quad + \sum_{j \in S_m} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n_k) \cdots w_i(n_1)w_i(j) \right) a_k \\ &= a_{n_1} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m_1^-) + \cdots + a_{n_k} \sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m_k^-) \\ &\quad + \sum_{j \in S_m} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m_j^+) \right) a_k, \end{aligned}$$

where $m_j^- = m - 2^j$ and $m_j^+ = m + 2^j$. Now observe that all three summations above with index i must vanish because of Theorem 8. Hence,

$$\sum_{i=0}^{2^{p-1}-1} \tilde{w}_i(m)B_i = 0$$

as desired. □

We end this section by presenting a result that is useful in characterizing sidelobes of Doppler tolerant waveforms in radar ([21],[6],[19]).

Theorem 12. *Let $A = (a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{L-1})$ be a mod- p PTM sequence of length $L = p^{M+1}$, where M is a non-negative integer. Write*

$$a_n = \frac{1}{2^{p-1}}w_0(n)B_0 + \frac{1}{2^{p-1}}S_p(n), \tag{12}$$

where

$$S_p(n) = \sum_{i=1}^{2^{p-1}-1} w_i(n)B_i.$$

Then

$$\sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m S_p(n) = N_m(L)B_0 \tag{13}$$

for $m = 1, \dots, M$, where

$$N_m(L) = 2^{p-1}P_m - \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m.$$

Proof. We apply (8):

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m S_p(n) &= 2^{p-1} \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m a_n - B_0 \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m w_0(n) \\ &= 2^{p-1}P_m(a_0 + a_1 + \dots + a_{p-1}) - B_0 \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m \\ &= (2^{p-1}P_m - \sum_{n=0}^{L-1} n^m)B_0 \\ &= N_m(L)B_0. \end{aligned}$$

□

4. XOR-Shift Recurrence

In this section we develop a recurrence formula for our weight sequences. Towards this end, we introduce the notion of an *xor-shift* of a binary integer.

Definition 13. Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z}$, where $\mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z}$ denotes the integers modulo 2. We define $a \oplus b$ to be the exclusive OR (XOR) operation given by the following Boolean truth table:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \oplus 0 &= 0 \\ 0 \oplus 1 &= 1 \\ 1 \oplus 0 &= 1 \\ 1 \oplus 1 &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

More generally, let $x = a_k \cdots a_0$ and $y = b_k \cdots b_0$ be two non-negative integers expressed in binary. We define $z = x \oplus y = c_k \cdots c_0$ to be the *xor bit-sum* of x and y , where

$$c_k = a_k \oplus b_k.$$

In what follows we shall write $a \equiv b$ to mean $a \equiv b \pmod{2}$. Observe then that if $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z}$, then $a \pm b \equiv a \oplus b$.

Definition 14. Let p be a positive integer and i a non-negative integer with $0 \leq i \leq 2^p - 1$. Expand i in binary so that

$$i = d_{p-1}2^{p-1} + \cdots + d_02^0.$$

We define the *degree- p xor-shift* of i by $r \geq 0$ to be the value (in decimal) given by the xor bit-sum

$$x_r(i) := x_r^{(p)}(i) = d_{p-1} \cdots d_r d_{r-1} \cdots d_0 \oplus d_{p-1-r} \cdots d_0 d_{p-1} \cdots d_{p-r},$$

i.e.,

$$x_r(i) = e_{p-1}2^{p-1} + \cdots + e_02^0,$$

where for $k = 0, 1, \dots, p - 1$, we have

$$e_k = \begin{cases} d_k \oplus d_{k-r}, & k \geq r; \\ d_k \oplus d_{d+(p-r)}, & k < r. \end{cases}$$

Example 15. Here are some values of $x_i^{(p)}(n)$ for $p = 3$:

$$\begin{aligned} x_1^{(3)}(0) &= 000_2 \oplus 000_2 = 000_2 = 0, & x_2^{(3)}(0) &= 000_2 \oplus 000_2 = 000_2 = 0, \\ x_1^{(3)}(1) &= 001_2 \oplus 010_2 = 011_2 = 3, & x_2^{(3)}(1) &= 001_2 \oplus 100_2 = 101_2 = 5, \\ x_1^{(3)}(2) &= 010_2 \oplus 100_2 = 110_2 = 6, & x_2^{(3)}(2) &= 010_2 \oplus 001_2 = 011_2 = 3, \\ x_1^{(3)}(3) &= 011_2 \oplus 110_2 = 101_2 = 5, & x_2^{(3)}(3) &= 011_2 \oplus 101_2 = 110_2 = 6. \end{aligned}$$

In fact, when $n = p - 1$, the sequence

$$x_1^{(n+1)}(n) = (0, 3, 6, 5, 12, 15, 10, 9, 24, 27, \dots)$$

generates the xor bit-sum of n and $2n$ (sequence A048724 in the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS) database: <http://oeis.org>).

Lemma 3. *Define*

$$E_p(i, n) := d_{p-1-u_p(n)}^{(i)}$$

so that $w_i(n) = (-1)^{E_p(i, n)}$. Then for $0 \leq r < p$, we have

$$E_p(i, pn + r) = \begin{cases} d_{p-1-u_p(n)-r}, & \text{if } u_p(n) + r < p; \\ d_{p-1-s}, & \text{if } u_p(n) + r \geq p, \end{cases}$$

where $s = u_p(n) + r - p$. Moreover,

$$E_p(i, pn + r) - E_p(i, n) \equiv E_p(x_r(i), n). \tag{14}$$

Proof. Since $u_p(pn + r) = (u_p(n) + r)_p$, we have

$$E_p(i, pn + r) = d_{p-1-(u_p(n)+r)_p}.$$

Now consider two cases: either $u(n) + r < p$ or $u(n) + p \geq p$. If $u(n) + r < p$, then

$$E_p(i, pn + r) = d_{p-1-u_p(n)-r}.$$

On the other hand, if $u(n)+r \geq p$, then set $s = u_p(n) + r - p$ so that $(u_p(n) + r)_p = s$. It follows that

$$E_p(i, pn + r) = d_{p-1-s}$$

To prove (14), we again consider two cases. First, assume $u_p(n) + r < p$ so that $p - 1 - u_p(n) \geq r$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} E_p(i, pn + r) - E_p(i, n) &= d_{p-1-u_p(n)-r} - d_{p-1-u_p(n)} \\ &\equiv d_{p-1-u_p(n)} \oplus d_{p-1-u_p(n)-r} \\ &\equiv E_p(x_r(i), n). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, if $u_p(n) + r \geq p$, then set $s = u_p(n) + r - p$ so that $(u_p(n) + r)_p = s$. Since $p - 1 - u_p(n) < r$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} E_p(i, pn + r) - E_p(i, n) &= d_{p-1-s} - d_{p-1-u_p(n)} \\ &\equiv d_{p-1-u_p(n)} \oplus d_{p-1-s} \\ &\equiv d_{p-1-u_p(n)} \oplus d_{p-1-u_p(n)+(p-r)} \\ &\equiv E_p(x_r(i), n). \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 16. *Let p be a positive integer. The weight sequences $w_i(n)$, $0 \leq i \leq 2^p - 1$, satisfy the recurrence*

$$w_i(pn + r) = w_{x_r(i)}(n)w_i(n), \tag{15}$$

where $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $r \in \mathbb{Z}/p\mathbb{Z}$.

Proof. The recurrence follows easily from formula (14):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{w_i(pn + r)}{w_i(n)} &= (-1)^{E_p(i, pn+r) - E_p(i, n)} \\ &= (-1)^{E_p(x_r(i), n)} \\ &= w_{x_r(i)}(n). \end{aligned}$$

□

Example 17. Let $p = 3$. Then $w_0(n) = 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and the other weight sequences, $w_1(n)$, $w_2(n)$, $w_3(n)$, satisfy the following recurrences:

$$\begin{aligned} w_1(3n) &= w_0(n)w_1(n), \quad w_1(3n + 1) = w_3(n)w_1(n), \quad w_1(3n + 2) = w_5(n)w_1(n); \\ w_2(3n) &= w_0(n)w_2(n), \quad w_2(3n + 1) = w_6(n)w_2(n), \quad w_2(3n + 2) = w_3(n)w_2(n); \\ w_3(3n) &= w_0(n)w_3(n), \quad w_3(3n + 1) = w_5(n)w_3(n), \quad w_3(3n + 2) = w_6(n)w_3(n). \end{aligned}$$

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